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Biography of Fake News with a Touch of AI: Dangerous Phenomenon through the Prism of Modern Human Sciences

Data Management Plan

6.0

01.06.2026

Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard. Corresponds with Horizon Europe DMP template.

History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	07.07.2025	Initial version
2.0	14.11.2025	Added: PDF, TXT formats, dataset documentation(README...); reclassified formats; extended repository specifications; removed APC costs info; mentioned IP blockers for publishing some outputs;
3.0	12.01.2026	Fixed information about original Verifée dataset. It will be available only from original authors because of legal IP reasons; Specified sections according MŠMT requirements
4.0	10.03.2026	IP reasons occurred not to publish content of CLI24 corpus.
5.0	25.03.2026	Published datasets sections added
6.0	01.06.2026	Improved description of access policy for dataset CLIC24

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Projects

We will be working on the following projects and for those are the data and work described in this DMP.

Biography of Fake News with a Touch of AI: Dangerous Phenomenon through the Prism of Modern Human Sciences

Acronym

dezinfor

Start date

2025-01-01

End date

2028-12-31

Funding

- **Ministerstvo Školy, Mládeže a Tělovýchovy** (Czechia):
CZ.02.01.01/00/23_025/0008724 (granted)

The project focuses on the analysis of the creation, spread, reception and impact of fake news using artificial intelligence. It combines methods from social, human and natural sciences in 5 synergistic research projects. It targets the linguistic, psychological and social dimensions of fake news, aiming to create tools for its effective and rapid detection and prevention. Through its key activities, the project connects research in the Czech Republic with the international environment of excellent research teams.

1. Data Summary

Non-equipment datasets

We also collect data from questionnaires and case report forms. The non-equipment datasets are:

- **Qualitative questionnaires** – As part of the qualitative strategy, cyclical interviews (min. 30 sets) will be used, supplemented by participatory visualization techniques with people from socially segregated localities of the Moravian-Silesian Region. Dataset will contain anonymized data from interviews.
- **Quantitative questionnaires** – surveys of respondents to identify their ability to identify fake news
- **News articles** from mass media websites in several languages (official and disinformation websites).

Re-used datasets

We have found the following reference datasets that we have considered for re-use:

- **Czech-ing the News: Article Trustworthiness Dataset for Czech**
It is available via: <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.wassa-1.10>. It is used in the project.

Owner of this dataset: Matyáš Boháček, Michal Borovanský, Filip Trhlík, Václav Moravec. matyas.bohacek@matsworld.io, michal@bravansky.com, me@trhlikfilip.com, vaclav.moravec@fsv.cuni.cz.

We will first need to convert the format before using it.

We will use version "1.10" of this dataset. If a new version becomes available during the project, we will stay with the old version. The original dataset will be available only from the provider.

We will use the dataset as follows: Dataset will be used as an additional source for comparing and analyzing linguistics features in many types of media.

There is no need to harmonize different sources of existing data in our case.

We will be using data that needs to be (re-)made computer readable first. We will provide machine readable, standardised metadata to others. For that, we will use the following formats: DataCite Metadata Schema. The data itself will be made available in computer readable form to others through a standard repository.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5bbab9>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.
- **Comma-separated Values (CSV)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.1943d4>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.
- **Joint Photographic Experts Group Format (JPEG Format)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nggi0j>
It is a standardized format. This is a format for long-term archiving described by ISO. We expect to have 5 GB of data in this format.
- **Rich Text Format (RTF)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.364323>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.
- **Document management -- Electronic document file format for long-term preservation -- Part 1: Use of PDF 1.4 (PDF/A-1)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.0ade3e>
It is a standardized format. This is format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 3 GB of data in this format.
- **Portable Network Graphics (PNG)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7xdxc2>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 4 GB of data in this format.
- **Extensible Markup Language (XML)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.b5cc91>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 4 GB of data in this format.
- **Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.YugnuL>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.

- **Tab-separated values (TSV)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a978c9>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 2 GB of data in this format.
- **Text File Format (TXT)** -
<https://fairsharing.org/6235>
It is a standardized format. This is open format for long-term archiving. We expect to have 1 GB of data in this format.

2. FAIR Data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Within the project, we have currently defined two options for long-term storing research data: **Zenodo** Repository and **ASEP** repository. We also created internal methodology rules for using persistent identifiers.

Zenodo

We use the multidisciplinary repository Zenodo to store research data, data management plans and other research outputs, where the [Biography of Fake News with a Touch of AI](#) project has its own community and these data records are also included in the communities of individual institutions. Zenodo Repository uses version DOIs and Concept DOIs (for all versions). If only minor metadata adjustments are needed, they can be made without creating a new version. However, if the correction is more substantial—for example, adding a new author or modifying the data file—a new version must be created. Repository Zenodo uses all important persistent identifiers – ORCID for authors, ROR for institutions and DOI for objects – datasets. There are internal rules on institutions which requires to use ORCID by scientists. All scientists already have its own ORCID. Scientists are instructed to associate for ROR on their ORCID profiles.

Metadata access and reuse: Metadata in Zenodo is licensed under **CC0 1.0 Universal** <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH, REST API and Sitemaps and they are harvested to the National Metadata Directory (EOSC-CZ), OpenAIRE, DataCite, **Google Scholar** etc. <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

Zenodo: Custom community of project Biography of Fake News with touch of AI - <https://zenodo.org/communities/dezinfo/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

URL: <https://zenodo.org/>
RE3data - <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>
FAIRsharing - <https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wy4egf>

ASEP

ASEP Repository The ASEP Repository is a multidisciplinary repository of the CAS with a general description. The metadata is based on the enriched UNIMARC metadata standard, supplemented with fields from DataCite. Metadata is created in the repository using a standardized form. Data from the ASEP Repository can be harvested and indexed. Data records are already automatically harvested (OAI-PMH protocol) e.g. to OpenAIRE, DataCite and will be harvested to the National Metadata Directory (NMA). Data records stored in the ASEP Repository are assigned handle (all ASEP records) and DOI (data records with files stored in the ASEP Repository) identifiers. Data in the ASEP Repository is accessible using the standard https web protocol. The ASEP Repository provides a place for long-term, reliable and secure storage of research data. The storage period is not limited. The metadata will be available even after the data has been made unavailable. In the ASEP Repository, there

is the possibility to link to other data and to link to a previous version of the data. Metadata access and reuse in ASEP Repository: Metadata is licensed under CC0 1.0 Universal <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/deed.en>. All metadata is exported via OAI-PMH and they are harvested to the National Metadata Directory (EOSC-CZ), OpenAIRE and DataCite.

URL: <https://asep.lib.cas.cz/>
RE3data - <https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100014032>
FAIRsharing - <https://fairsharing.org/6760>

While managing metadata we will follow:

- **Obecné doporučení pro metadatový popis výzkumných výstupů a výzkumných dat**
<https://doi.org/10.48813/yt6w-6h15>

We made a SOP (Standard Operating Procedure) for file naming. All folders and files are stored without any special characters like diacritics, or any of ,@€\$ etc. There are also instructions how to use folder structure in hierarchical order from global to specific folders. All team leaders were informed about those rules and ReadMe file with those instructions is stored in root of data storage. ReadMe file is accessible by any member of project. We will be keeping the relationships between data clear in the file names. All the metadata in the file names also will be available in the proper metadata.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All data cannot become completely open because of legal reasons.

By default limited embargo will not be used as data which are not restricted by legal reasons will be opened immediately.

We will work only with 2 types of access:

- Completely open
- Completely closed from legal reasons

Metadata will be openly available. Metadata will be available in a form that can be harvested and indexed (managed by the used repository / repositories) and available under CC0 license.

ASEP and Zenodo repositories guarantee long-term metadata lifecycle. Zenodo minimal metadata lifecycle is 20 years. The ASEP Repository provides a place for long-term, reliable and secure storage of research data. The storage period is not limited. The metadata will be available even after the data has been made unavailable.

Citation syntax of data is part of the README template. It consists of DOI, Authors, title of dataset.

All data will be owned by the institute.

We already published datasets:

1. **Morphology of Czech fake news from the viewpoint of quantitative linguistics.**

The dataset contains quantitative linguistic data describing the morphological profiles of five types of Czech news texts — credible, manipulative, misleading, partially credible, and unclassifiable. It consists of csv files, 3 python scripts and two figures (png). CSV files include values for the researched texts for a set of morphological indicators, such as the relative frequencies of parts of speech, grammatical cases, pronoun types, and deverbative adjectives. These variables serve as input for Principal Component Analysis (PCA). The accompanying figures show (1) the results of the permutation test for the first two principal components, and (2) the PC1–PC2 biplot with centroids and 1SD ellipses of data dispersion. The dataset is intended for quantitative linguistic and stylometric research, especially for analyzing and visualizing morphological differentiation among news types. Python scripts are published under licence CC-BY-4.0
Data files are published under licence CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17597332>

2. **Dataset and Code for: Tuning of Language Models in Eastern European Languages on Twitter/X**

This dataset contains the data and experimental code used in the study: Filip, T., Pavlíček, M., & Sosík, P. (2024). "Tuning of language models in Eastern European languages on Twitter/X." In Proceedings of the Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Language Technologies (Vol. 4092). CEUR-WS.

The dataset includes:

- text data from multiple Eastern European V4 languages collected from Twitter/X,
- preprocessing and cleaning scripts,
- experimental code used for training and evaluation,
- evaluation outputs (metrics, tables, plots),
- all resources required to reproduce the results presented in the article.

This dataset serves as supplementary material to the publication referenced above.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17865719>

3. **CLIC24 - Climate Change Multilingual Media Corpus 2024**

The CLIC24 corpus is a multilingual collection of journalistic texts focusing on climate change related topics. The corpus contains texts in Czech, German, English, and Spanish, collected automatically using a custom extraction script.

For each language, a predefined set of topic-specific keywords related to climate change was used. An article was included in the corpus if at least one keyword occurred either in the article title or in the article body.

During data extraction, texts were cleaned of navigation elements, advertisements, and other typical website noise. Articles identified as incomplete (e.g., due to paywalls) were excluded. Duplicate texts were removed based on URL comparison. Only articles published between January 1, 2024 and December 31, 2024 were included. Records without a reliably traceable publication date were excluded. The corpus documentation includes an overview of individual media sources, the number of included texts, and the list of keywords used for data collection. The dataset was created for linguistic and interdisciplinary research on media discourse, disinformation, and climate change communication.

Access and Licensing Conditions:

Metadata-only dataset. This is a closed dataset, only the metadata are open. Public files attached within the record contain only list of articles with URLs included in original dataset.

Due to copyright restrictions, the original full-text articles included in the CLIC24 dataset cannot be redistributed and do not have the license. License specification will be assigned individually based on legitimate data request. Use of the dataset outside the scope of the grant project requires permission from the authors.

Contact person: miroslav.kubat@osu.cz

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18924733>

4. **Graph Neural Network for Boolean Satisfiability (SAT) solving using message passing on variable-clause graphs. Dataset for Article "Neural approaches to SAT solving: Design choices and interpretability" and PhD Thesis "Graph Neural Networks for Constraint Satisfaction: Theory, Design Space, and Connections to Continuous Relaxation Methods"**

This record contains the dataset and associated code used in both the PhD thesis "Graph Neural Networks for Constraint Satisfaction: Theory, Design Space, and Connections to Continuous Relaxation Methods" by David Mojžíšek (ORCID: 0000-0002-3867-644X) and the journal article "Neural approaches to SAT solving: Design choices and interpretability" (DOI: 10.1016/j.ijar.2025.109609) by David Mojžíšek (ORCID: 0000-0002-3867-644X), Jan Hůla (ORCID: 0000-0001-7639-864X), Ziwei Li, Ziyu Zhou, and Mikoláš Janota (ORCID: 0000-0003-3487-784X). The dataset includes benchmark instances, generated problem sets, and outputs from graph neural network (GNN) models used for Boolean satisfiability (SAT) solving experiments. The code contains implementations for data generation, model training, evaluation scripts, and auxiliary utilities referenced in both the thesis and the article. In the published article, the authors provide a comprehensive evaluation of neural approaches to SAT solving, describe various design choices for GNN architectures, and analyze mechanisms for interpretability in reasoning over SAT instances. In the PhD thesis, these components are further contextualized within a broader

theoretical and methodological framework of GNNs applied to constraint satisfaction problems, including connections to continuous relaxation methods. This record aims to ensure reproducibility and reuse of the dataset and code across the research community.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18740315>

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **Czech-ing the News: Article Trustworthiness Dataset for Czech**

It is available under specific restrictions, which we will follow in our project: Dataset is available only for non-commercial use. To get access to dataset you must send mail to authors with a description of how you plan to re-use dataset. License prohibits:

- Replicate texts of low trustworthiness — either manually or automatically — with the intention to release them by any means.
- Create an algorithm that recommends or promotes articles of low trustworthiness.
- Produce any product supporting the spread of mis- and disinformation.

License is based on CC BY-NC-SA 4.0. <https://www.verifee.ai/files/license.pdf>.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Metadata will be published in repositories that support standard harvesting protocols, especially the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). In the case of institutional or national repositories, metadata will be automatically accessible to aggregators and indexing services. This setup will ensure the machine findability of research data and compliance with FAIR data management criteria.

We will be using the following standards (encodings, terminologies, vocabularies, ontologies):

- Journal Article Reporting Standards (<https://apastyle.apa.org/jars/>)
- DataCite Metadata Schema
- EuroVOC (used at Zenodo repository for keywords, classification of research)

We have created internal rules named “Rules for using persistent identifiers”. They are mandatory for all scientists and data stewards.

2.4. Increase data re-use

As explained in Section 2.2, our data cannot become completely open.

Due to privacy reasons, the data must stay in the same institute. We can use pseudonymization, anonymization, and data aggregation to make the data more openly available. For pseudonymization, we can make use of an existing 'trusted third party'.

There were found IP reasons why some of our data cannot be open. Currently IP reasons affects language corpus “CLIC24 – Climate Change Multilingual Media Corpus 2024”.

We will be archiving data (using so-called *cold storage*) for long term preservation already during the project. The data are expected to be still understandable and reusable after a long time.

To validate the integrity of the results, the following will be done:

- We will be instrumenting the tools into pipelines and workflows using automated tools.
- We will run part of the data set repeatedly to catch unexpected changes in results.

We have prepared internal template for datasets README files based on public <https://doi.org/10.57680/asep.0638679>.

README – structure contains Name of dataset, authors with affiliation (with ORCID and ROR), description, date and version, identifier DOI, funding, license, language, file list with data type and format, citation example of dataset, used tools and methods (for example anonymization process if relevant). All datasets will be published under license CC-BY-4.0 or newer by default with exception to legal reasons (for example IP). Versioning will be done in every new release.

If necessary, a domain-specific data dictionary is attached to the dataset. For general metadata fields, ISO standard codebooks are used (e.g. for formats, languages, and subject areas). The ASEP Repository uses codebook from the IS VaVal system for projects, large research infrastructures, languages, countries, and related entities. -

<https://www.isvavai.cz/is?s=prehled-ciselniku>.

Zenodo Repository uses version DOIs and Concept DOIs (for all versions).

The records in the ASEP Repository does not allocate DOI by itself but have metadata for evidence of persistent identifiers. ASEP repository allows versioning of data records.

Checklist for dataset is prepared. It contains checking encoding, null fields, possible sensitive data.

After the project ends, access will be adjusted as follows:

- Publicly available data will remain openly accessible through trusted repositories (e.g. ASEP, Zenodo) under open licenses (Creative Commons), without the need for access requests.
- Completely non-public data (e.g. protected due to copyright or ethical concerns) will not be shared but will be preserved in a secure internal environment and accompanied by metadata indicating the reasons for restricted access and the contact person for expert queries.

In case of incompatibility of licenses of source and output dataset, more strict licence needs to be applied to fulfill Intellectual Property rights. It will be explained also in output.

3. Other research outputs

We used Data Stewardship Wizard for planning our data management and creating this DMP.

The management and planning of other research outputs is done separately. Still, we benefit from data stewardship guidance (e.g. FAIR principles, openness, or security) and it is reflected in our plans with respect to other research outputs.

Software will be archived at Zenodo repository or ASEP. Mostly source code will be maintained at GitHub. Details of integration of both services are available at <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/github/enable-repository/>. Internal workflow and methodology for our processes will be available at project internal storage. Workflow and methodology related to research public outputs will be released at repository Zenodo or ASEP. DOI persistent identifier will be assigned by repository Zenodo or ASEP at release phase. For all public outputs we will use CC-BY-4.0 license or newer. Legal exceptions may occur, of course.

4. Allocation of resources

FAIR is a central part of our data management; it is considered at every decision in our data management plan. We use the FAIR data process ourselves to make our use of the data as efficient as possible.

We do not predict additional costs for data storage, data backup and long-term archivation. None of the used repositories charge for their services. Working data storage Microsoft Sharepoint is provided from already existing institutional storage resources and project budget is not affected by additional costs.

We will be archiving data (using so-called 'cold storage') for long term preservation after the project but also already during the project. The costs for archiving data will be paid out of departmental budgets from one or more of the project participants. The minimum lifetime of the archive is 5 years. Data formats of data in cold storage will not be upgraded over time. Archived data will be migrated regularly to more modern storage media (e.g. newer tapes).

As already mentioned none of the used long-term repositories (Zenodo, ASEP) charge for their services.

We have a reserved budget for the time and effort it will take to prepare the data for publication. For making data or other research outputs FAIR, we budgeted: 1400 man hours.

Lenka

Vaňková

is responsible for implementing the DMP and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

Tomas

Chorzempa

is responsible for reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use and maintenance within a data centre or repository.

Tomas Chorzempa, Barbora Kubátová, Kryštof Bořkovec, Kateřina Janderová are responsible for the management and proficiency of data including data processing, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability.

Tomas Chorzempa, Barbora Kubátová, Kryštof Bořkovec, Kateřina Janderová are responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

To execute the DMP, additional specialist expertise is required and we have such trained support staff available.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

5. Data security

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media).

We use Sharepoint storage from Microsoft. All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (<https://...>). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

We have also dedicated a local secured NAS storage inside University of Ostrava.

We will mitigate information loss risk for the project or organization. We will mitigate information leak risk for the project or organization. We will mitigate information vandalism risk for the project or organization.

All personal data will be anonymized as early as possible.

The archive will be stored in a remote location to protect the data against disasters. The archive need to be protected against loss or theft. It is clear who has physical access to the archives.

We are running the project in a collaboration between different groups and institutes. A collaboration agreement that describes who can have access to what data in the project is set.

Datacenters are located in EU. Backups are done on daily basis. Backup integrity is checked. Connection to storage uses TLS 1.3 and is encrypted and authenticated using QUIC, P-384, and AES_256_GCM.

Access Management to internal Sharepoint storage is based on role security groups. Each team member have access to resources based on his role in project.

For most sensitive data Sensitive Cloud provided CESNET can be used in future.

Integrity checks Sharepoint:

SharePoint uses various methods to ensure the integrity of blobs and metadata at all stages of the data lifecycle:

File hash stored in metadata: Hash of the entire file is stored with file metadata to ensure document level data integrity is maintained during all operations

Blob hash stored in metadata: Each blob-item stores a hash of the encrypted content to protect against corruption in underlying Azure storage.

Data integrity job: Every 14 days, each site is scanned for integrity by listing items in the database and matching those up with listed blobs in Azure storage. The job reports any blob-

references missing storage-blobs and can retrieve those blobs through the Azure storage soft-delete feature if needed.

Even if repositories Zenodo and ASEP do not have CORETrustSeal certification, they still offer very high data protection.

Backend Integrity Zenodo (CERN's Role)

Storage & Redundancy: Files are stored in CERN's EOS with two replicas on different servers and daily backups to a separate location. **Checksums:** Two independent MD5 checksums are stored (one by Invenio, one by EOS) to detect corruption or unauthorized changes. **Detection:** EOS detects internal disk corruption; Invenio's checksums catch external changes, as shown in past incidents.

ASEP repository:

Asep is based on the „Publication Activity Record“ module of the Advance Rapid Library (ARL) system. Metadata security is at the level of the IRIS database and its access rights control from the ARL application. User data is encrypted in the database, which is automatically backed up according to settings in scheduled tasks. ARL complies with GDPR standards. The digital content of the repository (files stored in the Content server) is secured from an application perspective by access through the Content server gateway, controlled by configurable rules. From a storage perspective, the content is secured at the file system level, the directory permission settings in the operating system and the backup policy of the virtual server administrator, so it falls under Veeam backups. Archiving is ensured by keeping the entire version history of stored files in the Content server, they are never deleted. Data transfer between the client browser and the ARL server is secured by the encrypted https protocol, with automatic renewal of Let's Encrypt certificates. The virtual servers running the live installation and shadow copies (geographically separated databases) are backed up by the standard means of the Academy of Sciences Library backup infrastructure – particularly the VeeamBackup tool.

ASEP:

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100014032>

Zenodo:

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100010468>

6. Ethics

Ethical approvals

The following project requires ethical approval:

- **Biography of Fake News with a Touch of AI: Dangerous Phenomenon through the Prism of Modern Human Sciences** (dezinfo)
 - case number: *OU-17466/20-2025*, status: *granted*

Data we collect

We will collect data connected to a person, i.e. "personal data". We explored General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) considerations and relevant materials. We ask the data subjects for their consent. We collect consent for our use as well as for reuse of the data. The data subjects will be informed as follows: Data subjects will be informed personally during interviews and will sign the form. In case of online questionnaires, tick box with link to the description and purpose of data collection will be included. The consent form will be available for re-users. The procedure for obtaining consent from data subjects is set as follows: Consent is obtained by filling in and signing the form or by tickbox in case of online questionnaire. The purpose of processing the personal data can be described as follows: Personal data are processed only for limited time before anonymization and aggregation of questionnaires is done by researchers. The process is strictly driven by Czech implementation of GDPR by legal regulation *Zákon č. 110/2019 Sb. Zákon o zpracování osobních údajů*.

In case of not publishing some of personal data we use legal reasons specified in *Zákon č. 130/2002 sb. §12a*.

The data collection is subject to ethical legislation. It is covered by ethical review. It involves human subjects.

7. Other issues

We use the Data Stewardship Wizard with its *CAS Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: 053avzc18:CAScommon:3.0.6) knowledge model to make our DMP. More specifically, we use the <https://avcr.fair-wizard.com/wizard> DSW instance where the project has direct URL: <https://avcr.fair-wizard.com/wizard/projects/778da78d-52c6-4cec-8d5a-385b3408dcda>.

We will be using the following policies and procedures for data management:

- **Pravidla pro žadatele a příjemce – obecná část verze 3, účinnost od 21. 06. 2024**
https://opjak.cz/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/PpZP_obecna_cast_OP_JAK_verze_3_web.pdf
Policy is mandatory to fulfill requirements from funding institution.
- **Pravidla pro žadatele a příjemce – specifická část pro výzvu Společenské a humanitní vědy: člověk a lidstvo v globálních výzvách současnosti, verze 3 – účinná od 20. 1. 2025**
https://opjak.cz/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/PpZP_specificka_cast_SHUV-verze-3-web.pdf
Policy is mandatory to fulfill requirements from funding institution.
- **Obecné doporučení pro metadatový popis výzkumných výstupů a výzkumných dat**
<https://doi.org/10.48813/yt6w-6h15>
Policy describes recommendations while using metadata for research outputs in Czech science environment.
- **Příručka postupů otevřené vědy OP JAK**
https://opjak.cz/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Prirucka_postupu_otevrene_vedy_v_OP_JAK_v1.1_web.pdf
Guide with description how to implement Open Science principals for OP JAK projects.
- **DataCite metadata standard**
<https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.6/>
Detailed information about how to fill metadata fields including syntax, relationships etc.
- **Zákon č. 130/2002 Sb.** Zákon o podpoře výzkumu a vývoje z veřejných prostředků a o změně některých souvisejících zákonů (zákon o podpoře výzkumu a vývoje)
<https://www.e-sbirka.cz/sb/2002/130?zalozka=text>
It is mandatory to fulfill legislation
- **Opatření rektora OU - OR č. 279/2025 - Poskytování výzkumných dat**
https://portal.osu.cz/wps/PA_Dokument_Manager/servlet/GetDMSFile?id=A1001001A25E15B42917H82773&tmp=ntp8976406849590417073.tmp422
Policy is mandatory for all scientists at University of Ostrava for publishing research data.
- **Směrnice pro ochranu osobních údajů Ústavu informatiky AV ČR, v. v. i.**
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/14mlewnoi3b6w4s76MK8zcp4qs8B6Q5d1/view?p>

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- **Zákon č. 110/2019 Sb. - Zákon o zpracování osobních údajů**
<https://www.e-sbirka.cz/sb/2019/110?zalozka=text>

It is mandatory to fulfill legislative act on the Processing of Personal Data.